

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and School Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

Laurentino Moreira¹, I Wayan Edi Arsawan², Lucio Ximenes³, Dr. Pius Bumi Kellen⁴

¹ Master's Program, Institute of Business (IOB), Dili, Timor-Leste

² Faculty of Business Administration, Politeknik Negeri Bali, Indonesia

³ Master's Program, Institute of Business (IOB), Dili, Timor -Leste

⁴ Faculty of Economics, Brawijaya University, Malang, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of work motivation, work climate, and principal leadership on teacher performance at Escola Técnica Informática-Dili. The type of research used in this study is quantitative research, namely research that aims to describe or explain something in accordance with reality, the approach used in this research is quantitative, namely research that is more about the "accuracy" of the description of each variable in the accuracy of the effect between one variable and another. Other variables. This research was conducted in four schools namely, ETI-Dili, ETI-Maliana, ETI-Baucau and ETP-Atelari which are all under the Klibur Mata Dalan Fundasaun (FKMD), the subjects of this study were teachers in the four schools with a sample size 74 respondents. The data used are data from questionnaires and interviews. For testing the questionnaire instrument, it was tested on Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili) teachers who were then analyzed for validity and reliability using the Statistics Product and Service Solution (SPSS) Version 21 application. From the multiple linear regression test using the SPSS application Version 21, on the results of the questionnaire, it was found that there was a positive relationship between the independent variables, namely Work Motivation, Work Climate, Principal Leadership on teacher performance at Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili). The results of the test for the coefficient of determination show that Teacher Performance can be explained by the variables Teacher Work Motivation (X1), Work Climate (X2), and Principal Leadership (X3), of 66.5 While the remaining 33.5% of Teacher Performance (Y) can explained by variables other than those not examined. As a conclusion from this study, there is a significant positive influence between motivation in the teaching and learning process at the Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili).

KEYWORDS: Work Motivation, Work Climate, Leadership, Teacher Performance

I. BACKGROUND

The country of Timor Leste in the current era of globalization is increasingly facing challenges because competition for human resources is increasingly competitive. The development of human resources is a very important influence for the success and sustainability of development, therefore the development and improvement of the quality of human resources is absolutely necessary. Educators or teachers are one of the most important factors in the context of developing human resources to educate the life of the nation and develop the Timorese people as a whole. Teachers play a strategic role in the delivery of quality education. The teacher is a resource element that greatly determines the success of education in schools, because the teacher is a human element that is very closely related to students in their daily educational efforts at school. Therefore it is necessary to empower the quality of teachers to be carried out continuously, and sustainably. Professional ability is one of the supporting elements for teachers in realizing work performance (performance). Performance is defined as a measure of work (performance), implementation of work, work achievement or work results/performance/work performance. There are important factors that influence the increase in teacher performance, one of which is work motivation. Apart from being influenced by work motivation, teacher performance is also influenced by the school climate. According to Marzuki in Supardi. (2014: 121), school work climate is the situation around the school and a quiet and comfortable atmosphere that is appropriate and conducive to learning which can improve academic achievement. According to Creamers and Scheerens in Supardi. (2014: 121), school work climate is an atmosphere that exists in a school. The school's work climate describes the condition of the school's residents in a state of joy and affection or concern for one another. Intimate relationships in the school work climate occur because there is a good relationship between the principal, teachers, and between teachers and students. According to Wirawan. (2007: 121), that organizational

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and School Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

climate is a relatively ongoing quality of the internal environment, experienced by members of the organization, influencing the behavior of each of its members. According to Supardi. (2014: 121), school climate is the atmosphere in a school. The school climate describes the condition of the school's residents in a state of joy and affection or concern for one another. Intimate relationships in the school work climate occur, because there is a good relationship between the principal, teachers, and between teachers and students. According to. (George & Jones. 2012), work motivation is a psychological force within a person that determines the direction of one's behavior in the organization, level of effort, and activities in the face of obstacles. So it can be concluded that work motivation is a collection of psychological processes that have power within a person that causes movement, direction, effort, and activity in facing obstacles to achieve a goal. Hariandja. (2013), argues that motivation is as the factors that direct and encourage a person's behavior or desire to carry out an activity which is expressed in the form of hard or weak effort. Meanwhile, according to Wibowo. (2010), that motivation is the impetus for a series of processes of human behavior in achieving goals. While the elements contained in motivation include elements of arousing, directing, maintaining, showing intensity, being continuous and having a purpose. According to Mar'at in Khoiriyah. (2000), that a person's work commitment is influenced by several factors such as motivation, compensation, training, leader functions, climate of cooperation, morale and conflicts that occur in an office. Teacher morale is an indication of teacher commitment. Mar'at stated that teachers with high commitment are those who have high morale, and vice versa. High morale is characterized by high discipline, work interest, enthusiasm and high motivation to work, being motivated to think creatively and imaginatively, consistently and always trying to find alternatives in teaching methods. Teachers with low morale will show disciplinary behavior, only fixate on one teaching method, less creative, less trying, and less motivated. According to Davis & Newstrom. (1996), organizational climate is the human environment in which teachers carry out their work or a series of work environment characteristics that are assessed directly or indirectly by teachers which are considered to be the main force in influencing teacher behavior. A conducive organizational climate is needed for teachers to foster encouragement within the teacher to work more enthusiastically. This means that the organizational climate of the school influences the level of motivation of the teachers. Thus the relationship between work motivation and work climate is a factor that influences each other on performance. Likewise, teacher performance is determined by work motivation and work climate. Based on these reasons, the researcher will examine the influence of these variables in assessing the performance of the Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili) Teacher, which is located in the aldeia of São Jose, Suco Comoro Postu Administrativo Dom Aleixo, and Munisipío Dili. Portal Governo de Timor Leste. (2011), Timor Leste National Education Planning Strategy 2011-2030 page 40 (p. 40), formulates the problems faced in Timor Leste education generally lie in the qualifications of educators (teachers) which include a lack of access and quality of training courses for teachers, to To cover this gap, the government, through the Ministry of Education, initiated various teacher training courses (in service training), including training on developing learning development plans (Plano lição), Method Aprendizagem (Learning method), Formação Conteúdo Currículo (training on curriculum context), and Formação Domínio Língua Português (Portuguese language mastery training course) this training aims to enable teachers to balance competencies that have not been mastered by the teacher. Instituto Nacional Formação Docente e Profissionais da Educação (INFORDEPE) or the National Institution for Professional Training of Teachers and Lecturers, detailing the objectives of developing teacher professionalism are: a). Ensuring teachers have the scientific knowledge, skills, and attitudes to utilize students' potential to the fullest. b). Develop a coherent and integrity system between pre-service training and in-service training, as well as initial and advanced training, with the understanding that the learning process is a lifelong process for teachers. c). updating knowledge and skills at every stage of the career as a professional teacher. d) Develop systems to strengthen and enhance existing teacher training institutions. e). Form a cadre of qualified trainers or instructors. The teaching profession demands expertise that can be pursued at the level of academic education, the demands for the development of knowledge and technology are getting bigger, so society's demands for quality education are increasingly being felt, thus the development of the teaching profession is based on the development of globalization making it a reference for every education stakeholder, so that the government's role in Improving the quality of education, one of which is increasing teacher professionalism through educational activities and teacher training (in service training). Timor Leste Ministry of Education Regulation No. 20 of 2010 concerning the *statuto carreira do docente* (professional status of primary and secondary school teachers) emphasizes that professional development of teachers can be through professional training within a certain period of time. These trainings are initial training, advanced training and specific training. The regulation is very clear that teachers are required to be able to develop their professionalism on an ongoing basis, so one of the means of transforming knowledge among teachers is through teacher work groups. Law of the Ministry of Education of Timor Leste No. 14 of 2008, article 48 emphasizes that teacher competence is a set of knowledge, skills and behaviors that must be owned, internalized and mastered by teachers or lecturers in carrying out their professionalism duties. The competencies referred to by the law are clarified in the Timor Leste Ministry of Education regulation Number 48/2008 concerning teacher qualification standards, emphasizing that being a teacher must meet the teacher's academic qualification standards through formal education levels recognized by the government these regulations are: 1) for teachers Pre-escolar (TK) academic qualification minimum education diploma 3 (D3). 2) Qualifications of academic education for elementary school teachers (Ensino Básico): must have a minimum education qualification of D3 to S1. 3) Minimum qualifications for junior high school teachers are D4 and S1 according to their expertise. 4) Qualifications for high

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and School Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

school teachers have a minimum bachelor's degree. Competency standards according to Law no 23/2010, Article 13 are: a) competency in mastering official languages (Tetun and Portuguese), b) technical-scientific knowledge competence; c) pedagogical competence; d) academic professional ethics competence. Teacher competency standards according to Law No. 14/2008 article 12 concerning Quadro Competencias Obrigatorias do Pessoal docente (teacher competency framework) include Official language competence, scientific competence, pedagogical technical competence, professional ethical competence. 1). Competence in mastering the official language: a. As a basis in the learning process, teachers are required to be able to master Portuguese and Tetun systematically, both orally and in writing, 2). Sensitive competence a). Demonstrate mastery of effective, broad and detailed learning methods in accordance with the curriculum context that applies in the learning process b). Have the capacity to manage, organize logically, systematically the context of learning material that is ready to be taught 3). Pedagogical competence: a). Have the ability to design effective learning and be able to embrace differences in the classroom as an equation. b). Have the ability to design lesson plans. c). Developing effective learning methods, and guaranteeing students' motivation to excel. d). Using a sustainable service system. e). Put forward patterns of discipline and student interaction. f). Prioritizing civics education for students. g). Have the ability to develop didactic material, in accordance with the curriculum, which is in accordance with the learning process. h). Have the ability to develop and adapt the context of the syllabus or teaching materials according to existing real situations and conditions. i). Mastering learning theory according to its specifications. j). Have knowledge and integrate the heritage, cultural values, and identity of the people of Timor-Leste into the learning process. 4). Professional Ethics Competency a). Respect and comply with basic principles, ethical standards, rights and responsibilities as a teacher; b). Carry out the rights and obligations that are manifested in the teaching and learning process; c). Ability to build good relationships with students, guardians, community members and school staff, in order to enhance the dignity of educational institutions and dialogue and communication between actors in the education system; d). Ability to recognize and promote social and school integration of different cultural customs and languages; e). A sense of fairness, dignity, independence, non-discrimination and common sense in student assessments; f). Promotion of civic and social respect for teaching, schools, teachers and students; g). Ability to assist in solving organizational problems of classes and educational institutions; h). Interaction with other students and teachers in self-evaluation of their teaching methods; i). the ability to promote continuous learning and training; j). Ability to promote civilization and citizenship. Professional teachers are teachers who are able to manage themselves in carrying out daily tasks. The theory of motivation emphasizes that a person will work professionally if that person has the ability and motivation. The point is that a person will work professionally if he has high ability at work (high level of abstract) and high motivation (high level of commitment). The teacher's professional ability is the ability to carry out tasks, which is equipped with competence (basic abilities). The principles of the teaching profession must: a). Have talents, interests, calling, and idealistic. b). Have a commitment in developing the quality of education. c). Have academic qualifications and educational background in accordance with the field of expertise. d). Have competence, e). Responsible for the teaching profession, f). Have income in accordance with its performance, g). Have the opportunity to develop professionalism on an ongoing basis. h) Has guaranteed legal protection, and has a professional organization. (Gunawan, 2017). Professional ability is one of the supporting elements for teachers in realizing work performance (performance). Hasibuan. (2014), stated "performance (work achievement) is a work result achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him based on skills, experience and sincerity and time", Sudarmayanti. (2011), argues that good work performance can be influenced by skills and motivation, skills without motivation or motivation without skills will not produce high output. The regional productivity development center explained that there are two important factors, namely mental attitude in the form of work motivation, work discipline and work ethic, as well as management/leadership. Motivation is the provision of driving force that creates the excitement of a person's work, so that they want to work together, work effectively and integrate with all efforts to achieve a Hasibuan educational goal. (2012). Wahjijumidjo. (2013), school as a formal education organizational unit is a forum for cooperation between teachers, staff, principals and students/parents of students. To achieve school goals, both quantity and quality are determined more by the role of the teacher, and the success of the teacher's work is greatly influenced by the principal through leadership that is able to create enthusiasm (motivation) for work. Talking about the quality of Human Resources (HR). Schools are complex institutions, because schools are institutions or institutions in which there are various dimensions that are interrelated and determine one another. Schools require a high level of coordination, because school success is the success of the principal as an effective dream. Leadership in general is an art or process of influencing others so that they willingly strive towards achieving organizational goals. Sujak .A. (2010). Then it was explained that the word lead has the meaning of giving guidance. Direct and walk ahead (precede). Leaders behave to help the organization with maximum ability in achieving goals. Leadership is the ability to influence, move and direct action on a person or a group of people to achieve certain goals in certain situations. Leadership is a managerial aspect in organizational life which is the most important position. (Terry. 2009), suggests that leadership is a relationship that exists within a person or leader and influences other people to want to work consciously in a task relationship in order to achieve a desired goal. The principal is a leader who must be able to coordinate and harmonize all available educational resources. Principal leadership is one of the factors that can encourage schools to realize their school's vision, mission, goals and objectives through programs that are carried out in stages and continuously. Because of that, school principals are required to have strong management and leadership skills, namely being able to take initiative and initiative.

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and School Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

Berdasarkan pengamatan hasil penelitian terdahulu, maka penelitian ini akan dilakukan untuk memperoleh informasi lebih lanjut tentang kepemimpinan kepala sekolah dan kinerja guru. Variabel lain yang Akan diteliti adalah motivasi guru yang kemungkinan juga berperan terhadap kinerja guru. Subyek penelitian adalah para guru Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili) yang terletak di Aldeia São Jose, Suco Comoro Postu Administrativo Dom Aleixo, Munisipío Dili. The main role in achieving teaching goals is a good classroom atmosphere, because all kinds of coaching and educational actions are directed at the class. Teachers with all their abilities and students with various backgrounds and individual characteristics, the curriculum blends and interacts, even the results of education and teaching are largely determined by what happens in class. Therefore, it is appropriate for the class to be managed properly and professionally and the one responsible for managing it is the teacher. The role of the school teacher in terms of duties and responsibilities is not light, both as a teacher (instructional function) and as an educator (educational function). They will always face various problems in all matters of learning. Another task of educators is to be able to align with other tasks at school. Researchers experience in the field that the Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili) teacher, which was founded by the Klibur Mata Dalan Fundasaun (FKMD) located in Aldeia São Jose, Suco Comoro Postu Administrativo Dom Aleixo, Munisipío Dili is implementing a Modular system in accordance with The National Curriculum from the Ministerio da Edukasaun Juventude e Desporto through the Direção Nacional do Ensino Secundário Técnico-Vocacional. Experience of teachers in the field facing problems in teaching. In the process, these problems arise in three periods, namely the period before teaching activities (pre-instructional activities), the period of teaching activities (instructional activities), and the period after teaching activities (post-instructional activities). There are many problems that arise before the teaching process begins. These problems can be in the form of teaching programs that are not yet perfect, such as how to plan a good teaching system, compile effective and efficient subject matter, determine methods and teaching aids that are relevant to the objectives and subject matter, and determine techniques and tools to evaluate the success of the process. learn how to teach. Because at Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili) there is no handbook for teaching teachers in the majors Técnica Linguagem de Programação (TLP/Software), Técnica Gestão Equipamentos e Informáticos (TGEI/Hardware), Técnica Multimedia, Técnica Construção Civil (Engineering Civil), Técnica Electricidade (Electrical Engineering), Técnica Electronica (Electro Engineering), Hotelaria e Turismo and Contabilidade e Comercio. So that the preparation of the material was compiled by the teacher himself and also taken from the Livro Manual do Professores which was printed by Ministério Educação Juventude e Desporto under the Direção Nacional do Ensino Técnico Vocacional, which corresponds to the Currículo Nacional do Ensino Técnico Vocacional, from various references is to be implemented within a period of one year in accordance with the total hours available (Orariu Karga) which has been set by the Currículo Nacional. Problems that arise when teaching, for example how to create a lesson system in accordance with the program, among others, how to manage classes properly, use relevant multimedia, use the right methods, how to motivate students. While the problems that arise after teaching how far the success to determine the assessment so that students can master the subject well. The principal as a leader has the responsibility to assist teachers in completing learning, in order to improve and solve problems that arise, both individually and in general. This fact requires a study by paying attention to the factors that cause problems in teacher performance, teacher work motivation and teacher work climate

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Definition of Work Motivation

Motivation comes from the word Motivation, which means encouragement of inner strength, while to motivate means encouraging to behave or try. Motivation in management focuses more on how to direct the power and potential of subordinates, so that they want to work together productively to achieve and realize the goals that have been set. Motivation is a process that explains the intensity, direction and persistence of an individual to achieve goals (Robbins, 2009). The three main elements in this definition are intensity related to how hard a person tries, direction is a goal while persistence is a measure of how long a person can maintain his business. to achieve optimal results.

B. Definition of Work Climate

Work climate is often referred to as organizational climate, because work is an organizational unit. Organizational climate is the internal environment or organizational psychology. Western experts define organizational climate as a physical element, where climate can be an attribute of the organization or an attribute of an individual's perception.

The school work climate is the situation around the school and a quiet and comfortable atmosphere that is appropriate and conducive to learning which can improve academic achievement according to Marzuki in Supardi. (2014). Creamers and Scheerens, according to Supardi. (2014), argued that school climate is the atmosphere contained in a school. The school's work climate describes the condition of the school's residents in a state of joy and affection or concern for one another. Intimate relationships in the school work climate occur because there is a good relationship between the principal, teachers, and between teachers and students.

C. Definition of Principal Leadership

Principal leadership is one of the factors that influence the quality of school quality. The application of the appropriate principal's leadership style will have a significant influence on decision making, as well as influencing teachers to do more efficient and

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and School Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

effective work to achieve good teacher performance. Permadi said. (2010), states that leadership is an activity to influence the behavior of others, or the art of influencing human behavior both individually and in groups.

Leadership is the process of influencing the activities of a person or group of people to achieve goals in certain situations (Blanchard Fan Hersey. (2012). Every time someone tries to influence another person, then that person can be said to be a leader and those who are influenced are followers. Here it is not at issue whether that person is a superior, friend, or even a subordinate. Leadership is the process of directing and influencing activities related to the Rivai group. V. (2009).

D. Definition of Teacher Performance

Suyanto & Djihad. H. (2000), stated that in an effort to improve the quality of national education, the government of Timor-Leste, in particular through Decree 23/2010, December 9, approved the Career Statute for Child Educators and Elementary and Secondary Education Teachers (Teaching Career Statute). Constitusauun Republic of Democracy de Timor Leste (K-RDTL) No. 14/2008 of 29 October, which approved the República Democrática de Timor Leste (K-RDTL) Constitution on Education, provides Timor-Leste with a framework for quality education. The curriculum, which at the same time represents the content and method of teaching, appears as the main instrument for carrying out the objectives of the first and second cycles regulated in the Republic of Indonesia Democratic Republic of Timor Leste (K-RDTL). Basically, it is a government policy which contains the government's efforts to organize and improve the quality of teachers in Timor Leste.

Michael G. Fullan. (2007), found that "educational change depends on what teachers do and think" This opinion suggests that changes and reforms in the education system are very dependent on mastering teacher competence.

III. FRAMEWORK FOR THINKING, CONCEPTUAL AND HYPOTHESIS

The frame of mind that will be examined is the teachers who teach at the Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili) in Aldeia São Jose, Suco Comoro, Postu Administrativo Dom Aleixo Munisipiu Dili, where there are variables related to this research, namely three independent variables (X) consists of work motivation (X₁), Work Climate (X₂), and Principal Leadership (X₃). While one dependent variable (Y) is teacher performance. With the explanation that motivation functions as a driving force for enthusiasm and enthusiasm for work to achieve something that is desired. Motivation for teachers is very important to develop professional responsibility in achieving educational goals. Professional teacher development is to improve quality which includes ability, knowledge, insight and creativity and discipline skills. Meanwhile, the principal's leadership is one of the driving factors for the school to be able to realize the vision and mission and targets of the school in order to achieve the programs that have been planned. With the relationship and cooperation between these variables, both between the teacher and the principal and supported by the creation of a conducive work climate, the relationship that arises is to form an increase in teacher performance:

Based on the conceptual framework above, the hypothesis in this study is as follows:

1. H1: There is a significant positive influence between work motivation and teacher performance.
2. H2: There is a positive and significant influence between work climate and teacher performance in organizing the teaching and learning process at the Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili) school in Aldeia São Jose, Suco Comoro, and Postu Administrativo Dom Aleixo Munisipiu Dili.

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and School Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

3. H3: There is a positive and significant influence between the principal's leadership regarding the work context and teacher performance in improving the quality of the teaching and learning process
4. H4: There is a significant positive influence between work motivation and work climate and principal leadership on teacher performance in the teaching and learning process at the Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili) school in Aldeia São Jose, Suco Comoro, and Postu Administrativo Dom Aleixo Municipality of Dili.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

The type of research used in this research is quantitative research or causality. This research wants to know the relationship between factors or variables of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and Leadership of the Principal of the Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili) School in Aldeia São Jose, Suco Comoro, Postu Administrativo Dom Aleixo Munisipíu Dili. Irawan. (2006), states that "The approach used in this research is quantitative, namely research that is more about the "accuracy" of the description of each variable in the accuracy of the influence between one variable and another and has a broad generalist area. The purpose of using a quantitative approach is to explain the facts that exist.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

To determine the effect of teacher work motivation, work climate and principal leadership on teacher work performance, it can be determined using multiple linear regression analysis, using SPSS 21 and calculating the results of multiple linear regression shown in the following table:

Table 1. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)	33.993	8.325		4.083	.000
MOTIVASI KERJA GURU	.167	.183	.107	.908	.000
IKLIM KERJA	.162	.215	.089	.754	.002
KEPEMIMPINAN KEPALA SEKOLAH	.199	.143	.163	1.390	.004

a. Dependent Variable: KINERJA KERJA GURU

Source: Appendix II

The multiple linear regression equation can be seen from table 5.11 based on analysis with the SPSS 21 program, the results of the multiple linear regression equation are as follows:

$$Y = 33,993 + 0,167X_1 + 0,162X_2 + 0,199X_3$$

The regression equation has the following meaning:

1. Constant = 33.993
If the variables of teacher work motivation, work climate, and principal leadership remain constant = 0 (no change), then the magnitude of the change in the teacher's work performance variable is 33.993
2. The variable coefficient X1 = 0.167
If the teacher's work motivation variable increases by one point (unit), while the work climate and principal's leadership remain the same, it will cause an increase in business performance of 0.167
3. The variable coefficient X2 = 0.162
If the principal's leadership variable increases by one point (unit), while the teacher's work motivation and principal's leadership remain constant, it will cause an increase in business performance of 0.162
4. The variable coefficient X3 = 0.199
If the principal's leadership variable increases by one point (unit), while the teacher's work motivation and principal's leadership remain constant, it will cause an increase in teacher work performance of 0.199.

Coefficient of Determination

Determination analysis is used to measure how much influence the independent variables have on the dependent variable which can be seen in the following table:

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and School Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

Table 2. Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary ^b									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
						F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.212 ^a	0.665	.004	21.376	0.665	1.101	3	70	.355

a. Predictors: (Constant), KEPEMIMPINAN KEPALA SEKOLAH, MOTIVASI KERJA GURU, IKLIM KERJA

b. Dependent Variable: KINERJA KERJA GURU

Source: Appendix 11

Table 2 using the SPSS version 21 tool, a coefficient value (R²) of 0.665 can be obtained. The meaning of this coefficient is that the relative contribution given by the combination of variables X1, X2, and X3 to Y is 66.5% while the rest is influenced by other variables not examined.

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing 1, 2 and 3 was carried out to test the extent to which the influence caused by variable X on variable Y used the t test (partial test).

Table 3 Hypothesis Test Results (t test)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	33.993	8.325		4.083	.000
	MOTIVASI KERJA GURU	.167	.183	.107	.908	.000
	IKLIM KERJA	.162	.215	.089	.754	.002
	KEPEMIMPINAN KEPALA SEKOLAH	.199	.143	.163	1.390	.004

a. Dependent Variable: KINERJA KERJA GURU

Source: Appendix 11

1. The influence of teacher work motivation on teacher work performance - Hypothesis 1
Testing using statistical product and service solutions (SPSS) version 21 variable X1 teacher work motivation obtained t count of 0.908 with a significant level of 0.000 while t table value of 3.21639 (df = 70 – 3 = 67). Because the significant value of 0.000 is smaller than alpha 0.05 ($\rho < \alpha$) and t count is greater than t table (0.908 > 3.21639) then this means that the teacher's work motivation variable has a positive and partially significant effect on teacher performance. Therefore, the higher the teacher's work motivation carried out at the ETI-Dili school (Escola Técnica Informática-Dili), the teacher's work performance will increase.
2. Effect of work climate on teacher work performance-Hypothesis 2
Testing using the statistical product and service solution (SPSS) version 21 variable X2 work climate obtained a t count of 0.754 with a significant level of 0.002 while a t table value of 3.21639 (df = 70 – 3 = 67). Because the significant value of 0.002 is smaller than alpha 0.05 ($\rho < \alpha$) and tcount which is smaller than ttable (0.754 > 3.21639) this means that the work climate variable has a positive and partially significant effect on teacher work performance. Therefore, the better the work climate at the ETI-Dili (Escola Técnica Informática-Dili) school, the teacher's work performance will increase.
3. The influence of the principal's leadership on teacher work performance -Hypothesis 3
Testing using statistical product and service solutions (SPSS) Version 21 variable X3 school principal leadership obtained a t count of 1.390 with a significant level of 0.004 while a t table value of 3.21639 (df = 70 – 3 = 67). Because the significant value of 0.004 is smaller than alpha 0.05 ($\rho < \alpha$) and t count which is smaller than t table (1.390 > 3.21639) this means that the principal's leadership variable has a positive and partially significant effect on teacher work performance. Therefore, the higher the leadership of the principal at the ETI-Dili school (Escola Técnica Informática-Dili), the teacher's work performance will increase.

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and School Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

DISCUSSION

Effect of Teacher Work Motivation (X1) on Teacher Work Performance (Y).

Work motivation is something that comes from within the individual that creates encouragement or enthusiasm to work hard. Work motivation is a very important determination in supporting individual and organizational performance. Motivation influences performance and behavior, motivation includes directing towards goals, in terms of considering motivation, it is necessary to pay attention to physiological factors, psychological factors, and the environment as important factors. Work motivation is something that comes from within the individual that creates encouragement or enthusiasm to work hard. Work motivation is something that can lead to enthusiasm for work, where strong or weak motivation determines the high or low work performance. The better the teacher's work motivation, the teacher will also be motivated to carry out his performance well. Work motivation as a driving force for the emergence of enthusiasm for work. Strong and weak one's work motivation affects the size of the achievements achieved. Work motivation is a driving factor that moves a person to carry out work-related activities, to achieve certain goals. Because as a driving factor for the occurrence of an activity, work motivation has a very important role for someone to produce certain performance. Work motivation is very important for someone to produce optimal performance. Leaders, managers and employees who have high achievement motivation will achieve high performance, and conversely those with low performance are due to low work motivation. Teachers who have high work motivation are characterized by behavior at work. If a school has teachers who have low work motivation, it will be difficult to realize teacher performance. Schools that have highly motivated teachers who are characterized by an interest in work and achievement motivation will devote all their abilities. Teachers who have motivational factors, will teach with enthusiasm, teach as well as educate, always develop their careers through creative ideas, teaching methods that are uplifting.

Work Climate (X2) on Teacher Work Performance (Y).

The work climate in schools is an organizational form that has its own culture that forms the pattern of a complete and distinctive system. The specificity of school culture related to the vision and ongoing educational process requires the existence of a school component in an organization, especially teachers. In addition to the leadership of the school principal, the work environment is one of the factors that influence teacher productivity and effectiveness. High or low performance of an individual is much influenced by the work environment and internal factors. Teachers who have high motivation will carry out tasks with more enthusiasm and carry out the work with greater responsibility. High enthusiasm and great responsibility towards work will result in maximum work productivity. A positive work climate is a condition that is conducive to creating productive work. It is necessary to create good communication between school members, openness, mutual respect, intimate influence, teacher involvement in making decisions, and appreciation for achievements that have been achieved so that teachers can carry out their duties with enthusiasm and pleasure so that work is carried out optimally. School climate is an influence among personnel, social and cultural factors that influence the behavior of individuals and environmental groups within the school. The creation of good quality teacher performance is caused by a good school climate. The existence of a good school climate greatly affects teacher performance, teacher behavior, the learning process in the classroom, and also influences teacher participation in school activities. Vice versa, if the school climate is bad, teacher performance will also be poor so that it will result in an unpleasant atmosphere among school personnel, the goals of learning will not be achieved, it will affect the achievements of students, it will influence between teachers. and staff become less harmonious, and teachers are less involved in making decisions. A conducive school climate and school organizational culture signifies a safe and orderly school environment, high expectations from school members, optimism, student-centered activities, school health are examples of a school organizational culture that can foster teacher performance. A conducive school organizational climate and culture is characterized by the creation of a safe, comfortable and orderly learning environment, so that learning can take place effectively. School culture or work climate describes the conditions and influences of work among fellow teachers, teachers and principals, teachers and other education personnel. This is the result of a conducive work environment. Conditions like this are needed by teachers and principals to carry out their work more effectively. School culture can be described through mutual support, cooperation, level of intimacy (intimate) and level of friendship (collegial).

Principal Leadership (X3) on Teacher Work Performance (Y)

Principal leadership is the ability of leaders to persuade and convince subordinates so that they are willing to follow their leaders with sincerity and enthusiasm. Principal leadership is a determinant of the progress or decline of a school. Professional skills are needed for the principal's leadership function to be successful in empowering all school resources to achieve goals according to the situation, such as experience and professional skills, personality, basic expertise, supervision, administrative competence, and professional training and knowledge. The principal's leadership is a spirit that is the center of the organization's movement to achieve goals. Thus, the performance of teachers will be influenced by the behavior of the principal. The leadership model in an organization can affect the success or failure of subordinates in carrying out their duties. Therefore, teacher performance can be influenced by the principal's leadership. The implementation of a leadership is very close to the behavior applied by the principal in influencing teachers, so that teachers will work effectively and efficiently. The principal is an example for teachers, if the

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and School Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

leadership is good, the teacher will carry out his duties well too. This will improve the performance of teachers in their implementation as educators. Leadership is an element of the situation that affects performance. Likewise, the principal's leadership is an element of the situation that affects teacher performance. Principals who carry out their duties by giving clear instructions to teachers will affect teacher performance. The school principal's leadership style that is effective and can motivate teachers will be the foundation for improving teacher performance which will have an effect on improving the organization. Leadership style is the norm of behavior used by a leader when influencing the behavior of others. The principal's leadership quality is reflected in the leadership style. Principal leadership that is liked by teachers and subordinates will create a conducive situation for improving the performance of teachers. The principal's leadership determines the management processes that exist in schools psychologically and administratively. If the principal is to become a leader, the principal must be able to pay special attention to teacher development programs that can affect teacher performance improvement. A good school will not find a bad principal or a bad school will not find a good principal. Many schools that failed turned into success and the good schools fell sharply. The success and decline of the school can be seen from the quality of the principal's leadership.

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation (X1), Work Climate (X2), Principal Leadership (X3) Together on Teacher Work Performance (Y).

Simultaneously the three research variables, both teacher work motivation, work climate, and principal leadership contribute significantly to teacher work performance. Schools in which there are principals who apply good and responsible leadership, accompanied by teachers who have high work motivation and a conducive school climate can improve teacher work performance. Many factors can affect the performance of a teacher in a school, including income or salary, awards, work motivation, attitude towards the profession, knowledge, leadership attention and responsibility, opportunity to obtain higher education, job satisfaction, work environment and so on. Teacher quality (teacher performance) influences many things, including the principal's leadership, organizational culture, and the work motivation of the teacher concerned. Teacher work performance is strongly influenced by school management factors, namely the role of the principal such as leadership role, managerial role, curriculum and instructional role. Work performance is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of an activity program in realizing the goals, objectives, vision and mission of the organization as outlined through the strategic planning of an organization. In essence, teacher work performance is the behavior produced by a teacher in carrying out his duties as an educator when teaching in front of the class, according to certain criteria. The teacher's work performance will appear in everyday situations and conditions. Teacher work performance can be seen in aspects of activities in carrying out tasks and ways of carrying out these tasks.

VI CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

From the results of research and tests that have been carried out by researchers on the influence of teacher work motivation, work climate and principal leadership on the work performance of teachers at Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili), Timor Leste. The teacher's work motivation variable (X1) is in the very high category with the salary indicator getting a percentage of 90.2%. The work climate variable (X2) is in the very high category with the indicator of the relationship between the teacher and the principal getting a percentage of 92.1%. The principal leadership variable (X3) is in the very high category with the delegative style indicator getting a percentage of 91.2%. The teacher's work performance variable (Y) is in the very high category with the indicator carrying out the evaluation getting a percentage of 94.3%.

1. The teacher's work motivation variable (X1) has a positive and partially significant effect on teacher performance (Y) at Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili), Timor Leste.
2. The work climate variable (X2) has a positive and significant partial effect on the work performance of teachers (Y) Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili), Timor Leste.
3. The principal leadership variable (X3) has a partially positive and significant effect on teacher work performance (Y) at Escola Técnica Informática-Dili (ETI-Dili), Timor Leste.
4. Variables of work motivation (X1), work climate (X2), principal leadership (X3) have the same positive and partially significant effect on teacher performance (Y)

Suggestion

1. By knowing that there is a positive influence between leadership and school climate on teacher performance both jointly and partially and knowing the characteristics that have the greatest influence on teacher performance at Escola Técnica Informática-Dili, then:
2. Teacher work motivation has a positive and significant effect partially on teacher performance. Therefore, the higher the teacher's work motivation carried out at the ETI-Dili school (Escola Técnica Informática-Dili), the teacher's work performance will increase.

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and School Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

3. The management of school climate data at Escola Técnica Informática-Dili is in the pretty good category. The school climate must provide a pleasant teaching atmosphere so that teacher performance will increase.
4. The leadership of the principal at Escola Técnica Informática-Dili is generally good. To make it even better, it is necessary to optimize the consultative management and supervision style of the teacher's performance in carrying out the learning process.
5. The leadership of the principal at Escola Técnica Informática-Dili is in the good category in line with the increasing demands of the community for the quality of graduates, so to improve teacher performance the leadership of the principal must be more effective. For this reason, school principals need to master various encouraging competencies.
6. Teacher performance at Escola Técnica Informática-Dili, is in the pretty good category. It is necessary to pay attention to things that contribute to teacher performance, and teachers must also improve the ability of these teachers so that they are even better.
7. To improve teacher performance, the school principal always checks and supervises teacher attendance at school, the guidance and supervision system carried out by the school principal is at work hours in the morning, afternoon hours and afternoon hours, the monitoring system can improve progress so as to monitor teacher attendance at school and in class.

REFERENCES

- 1) Achua L. (2010), Leadership Theory, Application & Skill Development 4th Edition, USA: Cengage Learning, Inc.
- 2) Arikunto, S. (2010). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktek*. Edisi : VI. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- 3) Asterina, Fitri and Sukoco, Sukoco (2019) Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah, Motivasi Kerja dan Disiplin Guru terhadap Kinerja Guru pada SD Negeri di Kecamatan Pagelaran Kabupaten Pringsewu, Provinsi Lampung. S2 thesis, Program Pascasarjana.
- 4) Azuar Juliandi (2013). *Metodelogi Penelitian Kuantitatif: untuk ilmu-ilmu Bisnis*. Medan : M2000.
- 5) Armstrong, Michael. (1999). *Manajemen sumber daya manusia*. Terjemahan Sofyan dan Haryanto. Jakarta, Indonesia: PT. Elex Media Komputindo.
- 6) Asri Wahyuni Shafarila, Endang Supardi, 2016, *Iklim Organisasi dan Motivasi Kerja Sebagai diterminan Kinerja Pegawai*. *Jurnal Pendidikan Manajemen Perkantoran Volume 1, Nomor 1*. Hal 1-1.
- 7) Assauri, Sofjan. 2013. *Manajemen Pemasaran*. Jakarta : Rajawali Pers.
- 8) Abdul, Halim. 2005. *Analisis Investasi*. Edisi Kedua. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- 9) Arismunandar, Y. (2016). *Pegaruh Sertifikasi, Iklim Kerja, dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Guru di SD Negeri Kabupaten Lampung Selatan*. Lampung.
- 10) Apri, Budiarto. 2017. *Manajemen Pemasaran Edisi Revisi*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Ombak.
- 11) Ary H. Gunawan. (1996). *Administrasi Sekolah (Administrasi Pendidikan Makro)*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- 12) Algifari. 2001. *Analisis Regresi, BPFE, Yogyakarta*.
- 13) Bakti & Elwan. L.O.M. (2019). *Analisis gaya kepemimpinan dalam meningkatkan motivasi kerja pegawai pada dinas pekerjaan umum kota kendari*. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/284470-analisis-gaya-kepemimpinan-dalam-meningk-6f35d66c.pdf>.
- 14) Bangun, W. (2012). *“Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia”*. Jakarta: Erlangga. Choiriyah, Umi. (2000).
- 15) Buhler, Patricia. 2004. *Alpa Teach Yourself. Management Skills dalam 24 Jam*. Terj. Jakarta: Prenada Media
- 16) Davis, Keith, & Newstrom, W., John. 2008. *Human Behavior At Work: Organizational Behavior*. New York: McGraw Hill International.
- 17) Dini Fitrianasari, Umar Nimran & Hamidah Nayati Utami, 2013, *Pengaruh Kompensasi dan Kepuasan Kerja terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) dan Kinerja Karyawan (Studi pada Perawat Rumah Sakit Umum “Darmayu” di Kabupaten Ponorogo)*, *Jurnal Ilmiah Dinamika Ekonomi dan Bisnis Vol. 1 No. 1 April 2013*.
- 18) Davis, K. & Newstrom, J.W. (1996). *Perilaku dalam Organisasi*. Jilid 1. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- 19) Davis, K & Werther, W.B. 2004. *Human Resources and Personnel Management*, McGraw-Hill Book. Singapore.
- 20) Daresh. (1989). *Supervision as Approactive Process*. New Jersey: Longman.
- 21) Faisal, Sanapiah. 1982. *Metodologi Penelitian Pendidikan*. Surabaya: Penerbit Usaha Nasional.
- 22) Fullan, Michael. G. 2007. *School Development: The New Meaning Of Educational Change*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- 23) Singarimbun, Masri dan Sofian Effendi, *Metode Penelitian Survei*, Jakarta: LP3ES, 2008.
- 24) George, J. M., & Jones, G. R. (2012). *Understanding and Managing Organizational Behavior*. New Jersey: Upper Saddle River.
- 25) Ghozali, I. (2018). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS 25*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- 26) Gulo, W. (2010). *Metodologi penelitian* : Jakarta : Grasindo.
- 27) Gunawan, H. (2017). *Pendidikan Karakter Konsep dan Implementasi*. Bandung: Alfabeta.

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and School Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

- 28) Gorrie, Mc Kinney, Murray. (2008). Faktor Persalinan Akan di Mulai. Yayasan Bina Pustaka Sarwono Prawirohardjo: Jakarta.
- 29) Gibson, R.S. 1990. Principles of Nutrition Assessment. New York. Oxford University Press.
- 30) Handayani, F. (2016). Hubungan Antara Kepuasan Kerja Dan Kinerja Bagian Produksi Pt. X Di Pasuruan. Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Universitas Surabaya, V, 1-12.
- 31) Hera Wasiati (2019). Pengaruh Environmental Uncertainty, Entrepreneurial Orientation, Pengambilan Resiko Berinovasi, Komitmen Terhadap Kinerja Organisasi. Upajiw Dewantara Vol. 3 No. 2 Desember 2019, ISSN 2614-0888, (Cetak) ISSN 2580-4553 (Online).
- 32) Hakim, Lukman (2017), Perilaku Keorganisasian, MUHAMMADIYAH UNIVERSITY PRESS.
- 33) Handoko, T. Hani. 2011. Manajemen Personalia dan Sumberdaya Manusia. Yogyakarta: Penerbit BPFE.
- 34) Hardjana André (2006). Iklim Organisasi: Lingkungan Kerja Manusiawi. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/99428-ID-iklim-organisasi-lingkungan-kerja-manusiawi.pdf>.
- 35) Hariandja, M.T.E, (2013). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Jakarta: Grasindo.
- 36) Hasibuan, M.P. (2014). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Edisi revisi. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.
- 37) Hasibuan, Malayu SP. (2014). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Cetakan keempatbelas, Jakarta, Penerbit : Bumi Aksara.
- 38) Hasibuan, S.P. Malayu, 2012. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Jakarta: PT. Bumi Aksara.
- 39) Hersey, P., Blanchard, K.H, and Johnson, D.E.(2012). Management of Organizational Behavior: 10 th edition. Prentice Hall.
- 40) Hadari Nawawi. (2005). Penelitian Terapan. Yogyakarta: Gajah Mada University Press.
- 41) Hanafi, Mamduh dan Abdul Halim. 2007. Analisis Laporan Keuangan. Edisi 2. Yogyakarta: UPP AMP YKPN.
- 42) Hamalik, Oemar. (2001). Proses Belajar Mengajar. Jakarta : Bumi Aksara. Jakarta.
- 43) Hadjar, Ibnu, Dasar-Dasar Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif dalam Pendidikan, Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada, 1996.
- 44) Hoy, W.K & Miskel, C.G. (2014). Administrasi Pendidikan : Teori, Riset, dan Praktik. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar
- 45) Idris, A. R. (2005). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Sebuah Gagasan dan Implementasi. Jakarta.
- 46) Ivancevich, Konopaske dan Matteson. 2006. Perilaku Manajemen dan Organisasi. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- 47) Irawan, Prasetya. 2006. Penelitian Kualitatif & Kuantitatif Untuk Ilmu-Ilmu Sosial. Departemen Ilmu Administrasi FISIP UI.
- 48) Khoiriyah, Lilik. 2009. Pengaruh Upah dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada CV. AJI BALI JAYA WIJAYA SURAKARTA. Skripsi, S1, UMS, Dipublikasikan.
- 49) Kusnan, Akhmad, 2004, Analisis Sikap Iklim Organisasi, Etos Kerja dan Disiplin Kerja Dalam Menentukan Efektivitas Kinerja Organisasi di Garnisun Tetap III Surabaya, Program Pascasarjana Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya;
- 50) Kerlinger. 2006. Asas-Asas Penelitian Behaviour. Edisi 3, Cetakan 7. Yogyakarta: Gajah Mada University Press.
- 51) Mangkunegara, A.. P. (2012). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- 52) Mudrajad Kuncoro, (2013). "Metode Riset untuk Bisnis dan Ekonomi" Edisi 4. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- 53) Mulyasa. E. (2006). Menjadi guru profesional: Menciptakan pembelajaran yang kreatif dan menyenangkan. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- 54) Mulyasa. E. 2010, Kurikulum Tingkat Satuan Pendidikan, (Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya).
- 55) Mulyasa. (2013). Kinerja Tingkat Satuan Pendidikan. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- 56) Mulyasa. (2012). Manajemen dan Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.
- 57) Mukhtar & Iskandar. 2013. Orientasi Baru Supervisi Pendidikan. Jakarta: Referensi.
- 58) Nasution. (2018), Metode Penelitian Naturalistik Kualitatif. Bandung : Tarsito.
- 59) Owens, Robert G. (2005). Second Edition, Organizational behavior in education. Engle Wood Cliffs New Jersey: Prentice Hall, Inc.
- 60) Permadi, D. dan Arifin, D. (2010). Kepemimpinan Transformational Kepala Sekolah dan Komite Sekolah. Bandung: Sarana Panca Karya Nusa.
- 61) Panjaitan, Januar Efendi dan Ai Lili Yuliaty. 2016. Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan pada JNE Cabang Bandung. DeReMa Jurnal Manajemen. Universitas Pelita Harapan. Vol. 11 No. 2, September 2016. P-ISSN 1907-0853e ISSN 2476-955X.
- 62) Pines, A. 1982. Changing Organizations: Is Work Environment Without Burnout (Online) <http://www.psychologymania.com/2012/11/dimensi-iklimorganisasi.html>. Diakses tanggal 27 Desember 2013.
- 63) Prawiro, Sentono, S. 1999. Kebijakan Kinerja Karyawan, BPFE, Yogyakarta.
- 64) Ika Rahmawati. Jurnal OE, Volume VI, Juli No. 2, 2014. Pengaruh Motivasi Intrinsik Dan Motivasi Ekstrinsik Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pt. Daekyung Indah Heavy Industry.
- 65) Reichers, A.E. & Schneider, B. (2009). Organizational Climate and Culture 1th edition. Jossey-Bass. San Francisco.

The Effect of Teacher Work Motivation, Work Climate and School Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance

- 66) Riduwan., Sunarto. (2015). Pengantar Statistika: untuk Penelitian Pendidikan, Sosial, Ekonomi, Komunikasi dan Bisnis. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 67) Rivai, Veithzal. (2009), Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia untuk Perusahaan: Dari Teori ke Praktik. Jakarta: PT.Rajagrafindo Persada.
- 68) Robbins, Stephen, P and Judge, Timothy A. (2009), Perilaku Organisasi, Edisi.12.
- 69) Sugiyono, Statistik untuk Penelitian Kuantitatif Kualitatif dan R&D, Bandung: Alfabeta, 2013.
- 70) Santoso, Singgih. 2017. Menguasai Statistik Dengan SPSS. Jakarta: PT Alex Media Komputindo.
- 71) Sedarmayanti. (2011). Sumber Daya Manusia dan Produktivitas Kerja. Mandar Maju Bandung.
- 72) Simamora. H. (2008) Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Edisi 2, STIE YKPN. Yogyakarta.
- 73) Singarimbun. M. & Sofian .E. (2008). Metode Penelitian Survei, Jakarta: LP3ES.
- 74) Sugiyono, (2009), Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D, Bandung : Alfabeta.
- 75) Sujak .A. (2010), Kepemimpinan Menejer Eksitensinya Dalam Prilaku Organisasi, Jakarta, CV. Rajawali,
- 76) Supardi. (2014). Kinerja Guru. Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- 77) Sutisna .O. (2010). Administrasi Pendidikan Dasar Teoritis Untuk Praktek Profesional. Bandung: angkasa.
- 78) Suyanto & Djihad. H. (2009). Refleksi dan Reformasi Pendidikan Indonesia Memasuki Millenium III. Yogyakarta: Adi Cita.
- 79) Steers, Richard M. 2005. Efektivitas Organisasi. Erlangga. Jakarta. Stringer, Robert. 2002. Leadership and Organizational Climate. Prentice Hall. New Jersey.
- 80) Suyanto, Djihad Hisyam, Refleksi dan Reformasi Pendidikan di Indonesia Memasuki Milenium III, Yogyakarta: Adi Cita, 2000.
- 81) Sergiovanni (1987). Leadership "What's In It For Schools ?". London: Taylor & Francis.
- 82) Yosefa, Misrawati & Hasneli, Y. (2016). Efektifitas Senam Hamil Terhadap Penurunan Nyeri Punggung. Jurnal Kesehatan Komunitas, Vol. 3, No. 1, November 2015. Diakses tanggal 27 Desember 2019
- 83) Usman Husaini. 2013. Manajemen Teori, Praktik, Dan Riset Pendidikan. Jakarta : PT Bumi Aksara.
- 84) Terry .G. R.(2009). Prinsip-prinsip Manajemen. Jakarta: Penerbit Bumi Aksara.
- 85) Triguno, (2015), Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Bumi Aksara. Jakarta.
- 86) Tesis. Yeni Murti. Nim. 500633604. (2016). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Guru, Iklim Kerja Dan Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah Terhadap Kinerja Guru Sekola Dasar Negeri Di Kecamatan Kota Mukomuko. Program Pasca Sarjana. Universitas Terbuka Jakarta.
- 87) Handoko, T. Hani. 2001. Manajemen Personalia dan Sumber Daya Manusia. Yogyakarta
- 88) Usman .U. (2013). Menjadi Guru Profesional. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- 89) Wahjosumidjo, (2013). Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah Tinjauan Teoritis dan Permasalahannya, Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- 90) Wibowo, 2010. Manajemen Kinerja, Edisi Ketiga. Rajawali Pers, Jakarta.
- 91) Wirawan. (2007) Budaya dan Iklim Organisasi. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- 92) Wahjosumidjo. 2017. Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah, Tinjauan Teoritik dan Permasalahannya. Jakarta: PT Radja Grafindo Persada.